

Phytochemical and pharmacological studies on *Hydrangea macrophylla*

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Abstract : Flavonoids present in *H. macrophylla* have been isolated and characterized.

Keywords : *Hydrangea macrophylla*, astragalín.

H. macrophylla (Thumb.) Ser. syn. *H. hortensis* Sm.; *H. hortensia* DC is an ornamental shrub up to 12 ft high, native of Japan and China and cultivated in the hill stations in India. The leaves and roots of *H. macrophylla* have long been used in China as an antimalarial drug, under the name Chang shah. It is reported to be more potent than quinine¹. Sepal colour of *Hydrangea* varies with the environmental conditions. The sepals of *H. macrophylla* are found to contain delphinidin-3-glucoside. The blue colour of the flower is due to the presence of aluminium and co-pigmentation of this anthocyanin, by 3-caffeoyl- and 3-*p*-coumaroylquinic acids^{2,3}. The present work involves isolation and characterization of the flavonoids present in *H. macrophylla* and investigation of the wound healing property, anti-microbial activity and SRBC membrane stabilizing capacity of the isolated astragalín.

Results and discussion

The fresh flowers of *H. macrophylla* was found to contain kaempferol (A_1) and its glycosides astragalín (G_1) and trifolin (G_2). Astragalín was tested for its wound healing property, anti-microbial activity and SRBC membrane stabilization capacity.

(A_1) R = H, kaempferol
(G_1) R = Glucose, astragalín
(G_2) R = Galactose, trifolin

Astragalín showed 98.90% of healing compared with the standard nitrofuracin ointment – a reference which was only

93.03% on the sixteenth day. Thus, this *in vivo* test exhibited 5% greater-capacity than that of the standard drug.

On account of the anti-microbial activity of astragalín on *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, the Gram-positive organism was susceptible to bactericidal property at 25 μ g of the drug, whereas the Gram-negative organism was contained only at 75 μ g.

Astragalín isolated from EtOAc fraction was tested for its SRBC membrane stabilization⁴ *in vitro* studies, showed an optimum value of stabilization at 200 μ g of the drug. A plot was drawn with concentrations in abscissae and transmittance in ordinates, and read at 560 nm in a photoelectric colorimeter. A biphasic property of the drug was observed, with a maximum protection at 200 μ g. Beyond this concentration, the curve becomes parallel to the X-axis.

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References

1. "The Wealth of India", CSIR, New Delhi, 1959, 5, 144.
2. J. B. Harborne and C. A. Williams, *Phytochemistry*, 2000, 55, 481.
3. Kumi Yoshida, Yoki Toyama-Kato, Kiyoshi Kameda and Tadao Kondo, *Plant Cell Physio.*, 2003, 44/3, 262.
4. R. Arivudainambi, D. Sukumar, V. Sethuraman, N. Sulochana and J. Sadique, 'An *in vitro* Study of the Anti-inflammatory Activity of some Flavonoids by HRBC Membrane Stabilization', Satellite Symposium on Traditional Medicine as Adjunct to Asian Congress of Pharmacology, 1985, Tamil University, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu, India, 1986, 139.